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Research Article

**DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF RP-HPLC METHOD
FOR THE SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF DOMPERIDONE
IN BULK AND TABLET DOSAGE FORM****Jerryphothula Pranitha, Koppu Udaya Bhanu Sri*, Dr.D. Venkata Ramana, Dr. Gadipally Sai Kiran**¹Department Of Pharmaceutical Analysis, Holy Mary Institute Of Technology And Science (College Of Pharmacy), Kondapur Telangana.**Article Received: July 2024****Accepted: August 2024****Published: September 2024****Abstract:**

The development and validation of a Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the simultaneous estimation of domperidone in bulk and tablet dosage forms are presented. The aim of this study was to establish a precise, accurate, and reliable RP-HPLC method that meets regulatory standards for the quantification of domperidone. The analytical method was developed using a Waters HPLC system equipped with an auto-sampler and a PDA 996 detector. Chromatographic separation was achieved on a Symmetry ODS C18 column (4.6 × 150 mm, 5 μm) at a column temperature of 35°C. The mobile phase comprised a mixture of methanol and acetone in a ratio of 35:65% (v/v), with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and a detection wavelength of 236 nm. The injection volume was 10 μL, and the total run time for each analysis was 6 minutes.

The method was thoroughly validated following ICH guidelines, assessing parameters such as specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness. Results demonstrated that the RP-HPLC method is both effective and reliable for the simultaneous estimation of domperidone in bulk and tablet forms. The method exhibited high specificity and sensitivity with a good resolution of domperidone from excipients. The developed RP-HPLC method is suitable for routine quality control and analytical purposes in pharmaceutical applications, ensuring compliance with industry standards.

Keywords: Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography, Domperidone.**Corresponding author:****Koppu Udaya Bhanu Sri,**

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INTRODUCTION:**Introduction to HPLC[1-28]:**

In the modern pharmaceutical industry, high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) is the major and integral analytical tool applied in all stages of drug discovery, development and production. It is ideal for the analysis of many drugs in both dosage forms and biological fluids due to its simplicity, high specificity and good sensitivity.

High Performance Liquid Chromatography (HPLC) is a technique that has arisen from the application to liquid chromatography the use of an instrumentation that was originally developed for gas chromatography. High Pressure Liquid Chromatography was developed in the mid-1970 and was improved with the development of column packing material and the additional convenience of on-line detectors. The various components of HPLC are pumps (solvent delivery system), mixing unit, gradient controller and solvent degasser, injector (manual or automatic), guard column, analytical columns, detectors, recorders and/or integrators. Recent models are equipped with computers and software for data acquisition and processing. The mobile phase in HPLC refers to the solvent being continuously applied to the column or stationary phase at a flow rate of 1-5 cm³/min. The mobile phase acts as a carrier for the sample solution. The chemical interactions of the mobile phase and sample with the column determine the degree of migration and separation of components contained in the sample. The mobile phase can be altered in order to manipulate the interactions of the sample and the stationary phase.

Types of Chromatogphy[1]:**Normal-phase chromatography:**

Mechanism: Retention by interaction with the polar surface of the stationary phase with polar parts of the sample molecules.

Stationary phase: SiO₂, Al₂O₃, -NH₂, -CN, -Diol, -NO₂, etc.

Mobile phase: Heptane, hexane, cyclohexane, CHCl₃, CH₂Cl₂, dioxane, methanol, etc.

Application: Separation of non-ionic, non-polar to medium polar substances. Disadvantage: Lack of reproducibility of retention times as water or protic organic solvents change the hydration state of the silica or alumina chromatographic media.

Reversed-phase chromatography

Mechanism: Retention by interaction of the stationary phase's non-polar hydrocarbon chain with non-polar parts of the sample molecules.

Stationary phase: n-octadecyl (RP-18), n-octyl (RP-8), ethyl (RP-2), phenyl, (CH₂)_n-CN, (CH₂)_n-diol, etc.

Mobile phase: Methanol, acetonitrile, water, buffer (sometimes with additives of THF or Dioxane), etc.

Application: Separation of non-ionic and ion forming non-polar to medium polar substances (carboxylic acids, hydrocarbons). If ion forming substances (as carboxylic acids) are to be separated, a pH control by buffers is necessary.

Reversed-phase ion-pair chromatography

Mechanism: Ionic sample molecules are ionically bound to an ion-pair reagent. The ion-pair reagent contains an unpolar part suitable for interaction with the unpolar hydrocarbon chain of the stationary phase. Stationary phase: Reversed phase materials (RP-18, RP-8, CN), etc.

Mobile phase: Methanol, acetonitrile, buffer with added ion-pair reagent in the concentration range of 0.001 to 0.01 M, etc.

Application: Ionic substances often show very poor retention in reversed phase chromatography. To overcome this difficulty an ion-pair reagent is added to the eluent.

Ion-exchange chromatography

Mechanism: Retention of reversible ionic bonds on charged groups of the stationary phase

1. Pumping System: The HPLC pump is very important component of the system. It delivers the constant flow of the mobile phase or phases so that the separation of the components of the mixture occur in a reasonable time. Its performance directly affects retention time, reproducibility and detector sensitivity. Three main types of pumps are used in HPLC to propel the liquid mobile phase through the system are as under;

a. Displacement pump: It produces a flow that tends to independent of viscosity and backpressure and also output is pulse free. But it possesses limited capacity (250 ml).

b. Reciprocating pump: It has small internal volume (35 to 400 μl). It has high output pressure (up to 10,000 psi) and constant flow rates. But it produces a pulsed flow.

c. Pneumatic or constant pressure pump: They are pulse free, suffer from limited capacity as well as dependence of flow rate on solvent viscosity and column back pressure. They are limited to pressure less than 2000 psi.

There are two type of elution process, i.e. isocratic and gradient

Isocratic: In this system, the things are kept constant throughout the run. In the case of pumping of mobile phase, the mobile phase composition is kept constant

throughout the run. The nominal flow rate accuracy required is $\pm 1\%$ of the set flow

Gradient: There is some change purposely incorporated during the particular sample run to achieve a better or/and faster separation. In case of pumping mobile phase, the composition of mobile phase is continuously varied during the particular run. The gradient accuracy of $\pm 1\%$ of the step gradient composition is typical.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

Instruments used:

HPLC from WATERS Alliance 2695 separation module, software: Empower 2, 996 PDA detector.

Chemicals used:

Domperidone from Sura Pharma Labs, Water and Methanol for HPLC from LICHROSOLV (MERCK), Acetonitrile for HPLC from Merck.

Hplc method development:

Trails

Preparation of standard solution:

Accurately weigh and transfer 10 mg of Domperidone working standard into a 10ml of clean dry volumetric flasks add about 7ml of Methanol and sonicate to dissolve and removal of air completely and make volume up to the mark with the same Methanol.

Further pipette 0.6ml of the above Domperidone stock solutions into a 10ml volumetric flask and dilute up to the mark with Methanol.

Procedure:

Inject the samples by changing the chromatographic conditions and record the chromatograms, note the conditions of proper peak elution for performing validation parameters as per ICH guidelines.

Preparation of buffer and mobile phase:

Preparation of mobile phase:

Accurately measured 350 ml (35%) of Methanol and 650 ml of Acetone (65%) were mixed and degassed in digital ultrasonicator for 10 minutes and then filtered through 0.45μ filter under vacuum filtration.

Diluent Preparation:

The Mobile phase was used as the diluent.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Column : Symmetry ODS C18
(4.6×150mm, 5 μ m)
Column temperature : 35°C
Wavelength : 236nm
Mobile phase ratio : Methanol:
Acetone (35:65% v/v)
Flow rate : 1.0ml/min
Injection volume : 10 μ l
Run time : 6min

Figure-: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

Table-: Optimized Chromatogram (Standard)

S.No.	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Domperidone	2.826	1825462	132551	1.6	5365

Observation: From the above chromatogram elution of peak is good and it shows proper tailing, plate count in the chromatogram. So it was selected as an optimized chromatogram.

Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**Figure-16: Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)****Table:- Optimized Chromatogram (Sample)**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count
1	Domperidone	2.825	1836584	138687	1.6	5426

Acceptance criteria:

- Theoretical plates must be not less than 2000.
- Tailing factor must be not more than 2.
- It was found from above data that all the system suitability parameters for developed method were within the limit.

Assay (Standard):**Table:- Peak Results for assay standard**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Domperidone	2.828	1836524	134582	1.6	5469	1
2	Domperidone	2.829	1835648	135629	1.7	5498	2
3	Domperidone	2.828	1836954	136584	1.6	5568	3

Assay (Sample):**Table:- Peak results for Assay sample**

S.No	Name	RT	Area	Height	USP Tailing	USP Plate Count	Injection
1	Domperidone	2.826	1826523	134568	1.7	5658	1
2	Domperidone	2.825	1825475	135698	1.6	5487	2
3	Domperidone	2.833	1825748	135688	1.6	5698	3

%ASSAY =

$$\frac{\text{Sample area}}{\text{Standard area}} \times \frac{\text{Weight of standard}}{\text{Dilution of standard}} \times \frac{\text{Dilution of sample}}{\text{Weight of sample}} \times \frac{\text{Purity}}{100} \times \frac{\text{Weight of tablet}}{\text{Label claim}} \times 100$$

The % purity of Domperidone in pharmaceutical dosage form was found to be 100.6%.

Linearity

Chromatographic data for linearity study:

Fig:- Linearity Data for Domperidone

Concentration µg/ml	Average Peak Area
20	668748
40	1278875
60	1886598
80	2458644
100	3028547

Fig:- Calibration Curve of Domperidone

VALIDATION CRITERIA: The response linearity is verified if the Correlation Coefficient is 0.99 or greater.

CONCLUSION: Correlation Coefficient (r) is 0.99, and the intercept is 44987. These values meet the validation criteria.

Precision:

REPEATABILITY

Table-19: Results of Repeatability for Domperidone:

S. No	Peak name	Retention time	Area(µV*sec)	Height (µV)	USP Plate Count	USP Tailing
1	Domperidone	2.824	1825463	133526	5426	1.6
2	Domperidone	2.827	1825685	132564	5369	1.7
3	Domperidone	2.833	1825426	133254	5428	1.6
4	Domperidone	2.833	1835687	132546	5385	1.6
5	Domperidone	2.836	1825642	132658	5364	1.6
Mean			1827581			
Std.dev			4532.982			
%RSD			0.248032			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD for sample should be NMT 2.
- The %RSD for the standard solution is below 1, which is within the limits hence method is precise.

Intermediate precision:**Analyst1:****Table-20: Results of Intermediate precision for Domperidone**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Domperidone	2.823	1836524	133658	5469	1.6
2	Domperidone	2.827	1836875	133695	5487	1.7
3	Domperidone	2.828	1836958	133693	5436	1.6
4	Domperidone	2.828	1836597	134568	5498	1.6
5	Domperidone	2.825	1845689	134598	5426	1.6
6	Domperidone	2.822	1845784	133659	5468	1.7
Mean						
Std. Dev.						
% RSD						

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of Six different sample solutions should not more than 2.

Analyst 2:**Table-21: Results of Intermediate precision Analyst 2 for Domperidone**

S.No	Peak Name	RT	Area ($\mu\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$)	Height (μV)	USP Plate count	USP Tailing
1	Domperidone	2.833	1325684	134568	5568	1.7
2	Domperidone	2.836	1332658	134579	5489	1.6
3	Domperidone	2.827	1334526	133659	5598	1.6
4	Domperidone	2.827	1325487	134526	5458	1.7
5	Domperidone	2.823	1336598	134758	5587	1.6
6	Domperidone	2.827	1326587	134569	5569	1.6
Mean			1330257			
Std. Dev.			4926.085			
% RSD			0.370311			

Acceptance criteria:

- %RSD of Six different sample solutions should not more than 2.

ACCURACY:**Table-25: The accuracy results for Domperidone**

% Concentration (at specification Level)	Area	Amount Added (ppm)	Amount Found (ppm)	% Recovery	Mean Recovery
50%	952225.3	30	30.068	100.226%	100.27%
100%	1863056	60	60.256	100.426%	
150%	2764762	90	90.142	100.157%	

Acceptance Criteria:

- The percentage recovery was found to be within the limit (98-102%).

The results obtained for recovery at 50%, 100%, 150% are within the limits. Hence method is accurate.

Robustness**Table-26: Results for Robustness**

Parameter used for sample analysis	Peak Area	Retention Time	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor
Actual Flow rate of 1.0mL/min	1825462	2.826	5365	1.6
Less Flow rate of 0.8mL/min	1818987	3.13	5126.3	1.7
More Flow rate of 1.0mL/min	1812658	2.589	5168.4	1.6
More Organic phase	1815897	2.514	5268.9	1.6
Less Organic phase	1805896	3.344	5264.4	1.7

Acceptance criteria:

The tailing factor should be less than 2.0 and the number of theoretical plates (N) should be more than 2000.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION:

This study focuses on the development and validation of a Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) method for the simultaneous estimation of domperidone in both bulk and tablet dosage forms. The primary objective was to create a precise, accurate, and dependable RP-HPLC technique that adheres to regulatory standards. The method was developed using a Waters HPLC system with an auto-sampler and a PDA 996 detector, employing a Symmetry ODS C18 column (4.6 × 150 mm, 5 μm) at 35°C. The chromatographic separation utilized a mobile phase consisting of methanol and acetone in a 35:65% (v/v) ratio, with a flow rate of 1.0 mL/min and a detection wavelength of 236 nm. An

injection volume of 10 μL and a total run time of 6 minutes were optimized for the analysis.

The method underwent comprehensive validation in accordance with ICH guidelines, evaluating parameters including specificity, linearity, accuracy, precision, and robustness. The results confirmed that the RP-HPLC method is highly effective and reliable for the simultaneous estimation of domperidone. The method demonstrated excellent specificity and sensitivity, effectively separating domperidone from excipients and other components.

The developed RP-HPLC method for the simultaneous estimation of domperidone in bulk and tablet dosage forms proves to be a robust and reliable analytical tool. The method meets all regulatory requirements, offering high specificity, accuracy, and precision, with an optimal resolution for the separation of domperidone. Its successful validation ensures its

suitability for routine quality control and analytical tasks in the pharmaceutical industry. The method provides a dependable means for quantifying domperidone, thereby supporting its effective monitoring and quality assurance in various formulations.

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